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Session

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Agroecology, Sustainable Agriculture and
Climate Change

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Zbornik sažetaka

Agroekologija, održiva poljoprivreda i klimatske
promjene

Smart management of land and water resources in agriculture in Bosnia and Herzegovina: implementation of H2020 SMARTWATER project

Mihajlo Marković¹, Nataša Čereković¹, Đurađ Hajder¹, Milan Šipka¹, Nery Zapata², Teresa A. Paço³, Erminio E. Riezzo⁴, Sabrija Čadro⁵, Mladen Todorović⁶

¹University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Agriculture, Bulevar vojvode Petra Bojovića 1A, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina (djhajder@gmail.com)

²Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Calle Serrano 117, Madrid, Spain

³LEAF - Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Center, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa, Tapada da Ajuda, Lisbon, Portugal

⁴SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL, Via G. Lorenzoni 19, Roma, Italy

⁵University of Sarajevo, Faculty of Agriculture and Food Science, Zmaja od Bosne 8, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina;

⁶Centro Internazionale di Altitudi Agronomici Mediterranei, Via Ceglie 9, Valenzano, Italy

Summary

Nowadays we are faced with the intensive degradation of important resources in agricultural production (land, water etc.). Processes like erosion, pollution and excessive tillage practices (land resources), unsustainable use and inadequate irrigation or drainage management (water resources) are becoming more intense. SMARTWATER project funded by the European Commission (EC) and coordinated by the University of Banja Luka (BiH) started in 2021 with main objectives to: i) reinforce the networking, research and innovation capacities of the University of Banja Luka (UNI-BL), University of Sarajevo (UNSA) and other BiH institutions in the field of sustainable agricultural water management and ii) increase the competences and fund-rising skills of UNI-BL and UNSA for successful participation in EU projects. SMARTWATER implementation includes several activities: advanced courses, summer schools, joint experimental studies, academic exchanges, stakeholders' meetings, dissemination and the development and promotion of smart water management tools. SMARTWATER network includes different target groups: teachers, students, early-stage researchers (PhD students), farmers, policy makers, final users, general public etc. Four main project topics include: (i) cloud-based smart technologies, (ii) new generation of satellite remote sensing data, (iii) water-energy-food nexus optimization and (iv) climate change impact in agriculture. Also, joint experimental studies are organized in three years and at two locations in BiH, being the aim of this task to investigate maize productivity under different water and nitrogen treatments. Most of these activities are already finished, but project team will continue to contribute to sustainable land and water management in BiH agriculture by implementing remaining tasks.

Keywords: SMARTWATER, twinning, networking, maize, irrigation

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